

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF HISTORICAL MONUMENTS IN THE EDUCATION OF MODERN YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM: GYZ GALASY (MAGIDN TOWER)

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Abstract

The article examines the history of the magnificent monument that has become the symbol of Baku - the Maiden Tower. The main versions of the purpose of the architectural structure and assumptions about the history of the creation of the masterpiece are considered. Several scientific approaches to the structure and purpose of the Maiden Tower are compared, although the architect of the early structure could not be identified, and some legends about this structure are covered. The historical significance of the architectural structure is considered.

The article also reveals the significance and role of historical buildings in the patriotic education of the younger generation. Conclusions were drawn on the preservation of historical buildings for future generations of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: patriotic education, Maiden Tower, historical monument, restoration, history.

Introduction. It is important to understand that the unique architectural style and mystery of the creation of the Maiden Tower - this cultural monument, continue to cause numerous disputes in the scientific community and attract crowds of tourists. It is no secret that the eastern architectural style is distinguished by its diversity and vivid specificity, while Giz Galasi is built into a ledge of the coastal cliff and rising in the south-eastern part of the Icheri Sheher fortress has no analogues either in the eastern or in the European architectural tradition.

The first mention of Giz-Galasy (Maiden Tower) dates back to 1403, when a native of Baku, Abd ar-Rashid al-Bakivi, wrote about Baku that there were two strong fortresses made of stone. One of them is large, stands near the sea, the waves of which beat on its walls. This information can be attributed to Gyz-Galasy [3, pp. 23-38].

The name Gyz-Galasy is associated with the Oghuz tribes. Considering the historical potential of the Maiden Tower, it should be noted that Azerbaijan is rich in historical cultural monuments. If books are the written memory of the people, then monuments are the stone memory of history. In the Middle Ages, the culture of Azerbaijan reached unprecedented prosperity and acquired global significance: literature, music, carpet weaving and other types of decorative arts. These words can entirely be attributed to historical monuments, which are unique works of Azerbaijani architects of ancient times and the Middle Ages.

National treasures and pearls of architecture include such historical and cultural monuments as: Mausoleum of Momine Khatun in Nakhchivan (1186), Karabaglar (1162), Gulistan, XVIII century, Domes of Barda (1322), Palace of the Shirvanshahs (XV century), dating back to the Albanian period temples "Kilsedag", historical monument "Diribaba" in the village of Mirza, Shemakha region (1405), Khudafarin bridge on the Araks River (XII century), Palace of

Sheki Khans (XVIII century), monuments of Shushi, Chukhur Hamam and Juma Meschid in Quba (late 18th century) and hundreds of other historical monuments [9]. And all historical monuments serve as an educational basis for feeding the patriotic views of modern youth.

Main part. The legends about the Maiden Tower are also ambiguous: according to one of them, Gyz-Galasy tells of a passionate love between the daughter of the Shah and a fisherman. Every day, to see his beloved, the fisherman came to the tower by the sea. He walked steadily along the surface of the sea "on the sails of faith and love." Time passed. Their love grew stronger and stronger and gave the lovers strength to overcome any obstacles in their path. But one day, on the way back, the fisherman's faith was shaken, and he began to drown. The daughter of the Shah, who followed her lover with her gaze, saw that he was drowning, threw herself from the tower to save him and drowned herself, for the fear in her soul exceeded her faith. Since that time, this tower began to be called among the people Gyz-Galasy (Maiden Tower), becoming a symbol of the greatness of faith and love, purity and courage [4]. Here, too, there is a reference to instilling in young people faith and love for their small homeland. According to another version, the Shah was in love with his own daughter and, avoiding shame, the girl committed suicide by throwing herself into the sea. It can be assumed that the possibility of marriage between father and daughter determines the origin of the legend in the pre-Islamic period. The important thing is that the legend testifies that the Caspian Sea splashed at the very foot of the tower. The Maiden Tower means no less to Baku than the Eiffel Tower to Paris. There is still controversy surrounding the construction date and purpose of the Maiden Tower; the tower inspires researchers with its extraordinary shape. It is doubtful that the Maiden Tower was built for defensive purposes, although a similar version existed for many

years. The archaic tower structure of the city of Baku could have arisen as a synthesis of the architecture of the Caspian and Medes, nomadic tribes [8, pp. 22-23].

There are assumptions that the tower was originally built as a fire temple (the word "gala" in the Azerbaijani language also means "to make a fire"), an observatory, a Zoroastrian dakhma, but none of the hypotheses put forward is indisputable. S. Ashurbeyli noted that the Baku zone already in the early Middle Ages was noted in sources as an area where inextinguishable fires burned, in the words of the Hun leaders "... where the flame rises from an underwater rock..." (ex petra maritima flamma ardet) [3, pp.23-38]. This information, according to N. Khanykov, "undoubtedly refers to the Baku eternal flames."

On the outer side of the wall of the Maiden Tower, at a height of 14 meters above the lower door, on a stone tablet measuring 4x0.6 m there is an entry written in Kufi handwriting [1]. The background of the recording is carved from stone, the words are located in two lines. This entry was first read by the famous orientalist N. Khanykov: "The dome (vault) of Masud ibn Davud." Scientists, considering the monuments of the Middle Ages, came to the conclusion that tall monuments with a domed roof could be either a tomb or an observatory [10, p.51]. The fact that the inscription contains the word "dome" brings us closer to the idea that the Maiden Tower was an observatory. Rashid Ardin (XIII-XIV centuries) and Wassaf (XIV century), describing the observatories in Maragha and Tabriz, note the presence of high domes in these observatories. During excavations at the Maragha Observatory, the circle of this dome was discovered [2, p.20].

During the Derbendi dynasty, Gyz-Galasy was a defensive structure that was part of the general system of structures of the Shirvanshahs, and served as a beacon, from where, in case of danger, signals of threatening danger were given during the day with the help of smoke, and at night with fire [4]. In the villages of Baku and around there were 19 towers, if according to Pakhomov we add here Gyz Galasy, and Jabekhanu, and the towers around Baku and other buildings, the number will reach somewhere around 30 towers [10].

As already noted, a small Kufi inscription is mounted on the southwestern wall of the Tower. In Khanykov's Arabic text, the first word is given in the form "qubba", which in Russian translation means "daxme", and in later inscriptions it also appears in the meaning of "tomb". It should be read as follows: "The Domes of Masud ibn Dawood." Based on paleographic features, the inscription dates back to the 12th century, but this date is associated with the renovation of the tower. In the 12th century, the Maiden Tower was part of the defensive system of the city of Baku. The name of the Maiden Tower is, in all likelihood, a distorted form of Gaz-Galasa, that is, "overwatch tower." The tower also served as a lighthouse. During the day, smoke and in the evening, fire lit on the tower, signaled the approach of danger from the sea and land to the remaining defensive structures, of which there were more than thirty on the Absheron Peninsula [5, p.9]. According to one version, the Sassanian king Ardashir (III century) further strengthens the service at the temples and

orders to "unquenchably maintain the fire of Hormuzd on the altar in Bhagavan". In Gyz-Galasy there were seven hearth-altars [6, p.40]. In different historical eras, the tower served as a citadel, a lighthouse and a religious building. An interesting presentation of historical monuments plays a huge role in instilling love for the Motherland from early childhood. Teachers emphasize excursions to these places to visually understand the significance of historical facts in education.

In the education of patriotic feelings among high school students, historical events and facts about them, which are presented by teachers and mentors in lessons and extracurricular hours, have a huge influence. High school students themselves can evaluate these phenomena, and also have their own point of view on the material provided. With this, the younger generation, drawing their own conclusions, can organize a lesson-seminar on the topic of patriotism for younger schoolchildren. Divided into teams, they can independently conduct research work to study historical facts.

Let us consider the features of research from the point of view of the historicism of the Maiden Tower. The architectural monument occupies a special place in the research of Sayapin. He offers the reader the following description: "Imagine that the vaults are intact. Imagine, by analogy with the small Mardakan tower, that there is a hole in the center of each diaphragm. That these holes are located one above the other with mathematical precision, and you could see during the day - the stars, the light of the zodiac" [4]. Sayapin comes to the conclusion that the towers with fortresses are Zoroastrian temples, where religious festivals were held and sacrifices were made.

Academic historian I.I. also wrote that the Maiden Tower was a religious building. Meshchaninov. This concept is then developed by the head of the department Az. Institute of Civil Engineering, Doctor of Architecture D.A. Akhundov. In "Reports of the Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan SSR" an article by M.A. Nabiev "The Secret of the Baku Gyz Galasi". A detailed study of its internal and external structures, according to the author, "leads to the firm conviction that it is not a defensive structure, not a lighthouse, and certainly not a signal tower. It is a Zoroastrian religious building, called in Pahlavi the term "dakhma" [7, p.93]. Such towers, called dakhma or towers of silence, now exist in India - Bombay, where the largest colony of Zoroastrians who fled here from Iran and were called Parsis in India is still preserved.

Akhundov D.A., having analyzed the drawings of Baku from the XVIIIth - XIXth centuries, believing that they also show the remains of a fortress, locates this fortress somewhere to the east of the old city. This Salkhim fortress, the remains of which date back to the 60s of the last century, according to academician B.A. Dorna, visible from the city. In general, back in the 70s of the XVIIIth century, judging by the drawing by S.G. Gmelin, there were 3 fortress towers around Baku on the hills. And then the location of the Maiden Tower becomes clear; it was built far from the city, as this is explained by the presence of a rock here, on which this powerful structure could be erected. At the same time,

Baku residents also moved here behind the walls. Judging by archaeological excavations, this happened in the VIIIth-IXth centuries. This means that the Maiden Tower was built long before that.

The oldest such building was discovered in Kabala and dates back to the I st century AD. This is the lower age limit of the tower. The upper limit can be determined by comparing the color of the stones of the Maiden Tower and the Mohammed ibn Abu Bakr Mosque, which is located in the fortress and was built in 1078-79. Moreover, both buildings are made of the same type of limestone; the stones of the tower are much darker, which means they are several hundred years older than the Mohammed Mosque. The upper limit is no later than the IXth-Xth centuries. S.B. Ashurbeyli put forward the assumption of the construction of Giz Galasa in the 1st century AD, M.A. Nabiev in the VIth century.

The historian of Azerbaijani architecture L. Bretnitsky believed that it was erected in 2 stages: the lower part of the monument, up to a height of 13.7 meters, was built in the 5th-6th centuries, and the upper part was completed in the 12th century.

A special place is occupied by the religious justifications of the Maiden Tower. According to Kazieva, the Maiden Tower is the "flaming sword" indicated in the Bible, guarding the path to the "tree of life" [6, p.40]. There is also information about the reconstruction of the upper part of the tower in the 19th century in order to adapt it to a lighthouse. The Baku lighthouse, located on the Maiden Tower, began to shine on June 13, 1858. Until that time, a serf flag, a flagpole, was raised on it, which was provided for by the measurements and plan of 1808 [7, p.93].

Conclusions. The Maiden Tower (XII century, height 30 m, 5 m at the base and 4 m at the top), which rises in the coastal part of the city of Icheri Sheher, is a unique feature of the city of Baku. In plan, it symbolizes the shape of the buta or flame of fire, since Azerbaijan is the land of fire. The legends that envelop this building certainly fuel tourist interest; it also influences the education of young people as a historical fact, serving as a clear visual example.

Summing up, it should be stated that the role of historical and cultural monuments in the study of the history of the Azerbaijani people is great, and historical monuments play a very important role in the education of the younger generation. Since the second half of the 19th century, the richest material cultural values of Azerbaijan have attracted the attention of outstanding Russian and foreign scientists and travelers. However,

in no case should we forget about the enormous work of Azerbaijani scientists and researchers, the contribution they made to the study, preservation, research and promotion of the cultural heritage of Azerbaijan.

To date, hundreds of monuments have been explored and registered. Excursions to historical places occupy a special place in the educational system of the republic, but we offer compulsory visits to historical places for schoolchildren and students as part of the curriculum and state support for organizing transport. Based on the results of these studies, hundreds of books, monographs and scientific articles have been published. Approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the "State Program for the development and improvement of activities for the restoration and preservation of historical and cultural monuments and reserves" [9] is a new milestone in the history of Azerbaijani archeology and culture in general, and also affects the education of the new generation within the framework of folk traditions and in the spirit of patriotism.

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